

Vol. 1 No. 2 (September- 2024)

<https://qomar.uz/index.php/RIBIJ>

ISSN: 3060-4753

Funding Panacea for Development of Green Campus Initiatives in Nigerian Higher Education Institutions

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Received: 2024 20, August

Accepted: 2024 28, August

Published: 2024 21, September

Published under peer review:

Doctor of Philosophy(PhD)

Dotsent

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Annotation: This paper critically looked at the roles of funding in the implementation of green campus initiative in the Nigerian tertiary institutions. The authors used secondary data. They collected the data from print and online publications which includes; seminar papers, documentary on green programmes, international books and conferences. The paper concluded that without adequate funding nothing can be achieved in the programme of green campus in the Nigerian tertiary institutions. Adequate funding will support development of green campus initiative programme, green curriculum and green infrastructure facilities in all the tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the paper recommends that federal government should establish a special intervention funding plans for the implementation of the green campus initiative in the Nigerian tertiary institutions. The international institutions and private institutions should be integrated into the funding programme of the green campus initiative in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Government should set up effective monitoring and evaluation to monitor the use of the funds is allocated for the implementation of green campus initiatives in the Nigerian tertiary institutions to curtail mismanagement of the funds.

Keywords: Funding, Green Campus Initiatives, Tertiary education, Green University.

INTRODUCTION(KIRISH)

Tertiary education is an education designed for national development through manpower training and retraining. Tertiary institutions is an industry for manpower development via teaching, research and community service. The word tertiary, simply means of the third rank or order, and tertiary level of education in Nigeria, based on the aforementioned meaning, implies that tertiary education in Nigeria is the third order of education which can also be referred to as higher education (Okai, & Botimi –Slaboh 2019). Tertiary education is a front liner amongst the tiers of education and is considered as the icon for national development and transformation, implying that every skill, knowledge and information gained through this means is the vehicle for productivity, wealth creation, prosperity, good health and healthy living, competitiveness, communication, expansion, scientific and technological advancement (Ofojebe & Chukwuma,2015).

Tertiary education is defined by National policy on Education (2013) as the education given after Post Basic Education in institutions such as Universities and Inter-University Centres such as the Nigeria French Language Village, Nigeria Arabic Language Village, National Institute of Nigerian Languages, institutions such as Innovation Enterprise Institutions (IEIs), and Colleges of Education, Monotechnics, Polytechnics, and other specialized institutions such as Colleges of Agriculture, Schools of Health and Technology and the National Teachers' Institutes (NTI). The goals of tertiary education according to the FGN National Policy on Education (2013), shall be to: contribute to national development through high level manpower training; provide accessible and affordable quality learning opportunities in formal and informal education in response to the needs and interests of all Nigerians; provide high quality career counseling and lifelong learning program that prepare students with the knowledge and skills for self-reliance and the world of work; reduce skill shortages through the production of skilled manpower relevant to the needs of the labor market; promote and encourage scholarship, entrepreneurship and community service; forge and cement national unity; and promote national and international understanding and interaction.

To ensure environment sustainable and development across the countries the United Nations launched green campus initiative programme for higher institutions. Sherif (2023) noted that UNEP includes “green” University networks that are being formed in Africa and other developing regions. It aims to improve the sustainability of Universities by integrating strategies to develop resilience, low carbon and aspects of sustainability in education (training, University infrastructure, improvement of the educational, recreational and educational environment for students), inside and outside universities. The UNEP Networks will also help universities mainstream the UNEP Green University Interior and Exterior Design Toolkit into their day-to-day functions through green University developments and practices, curriculum development, and community and student engagement.

Some tertiary institutions in Nigeria has commence the implementation of green campus initiative programme. Naturenews (2023) has maintained some Nigerian campuses have undertook steps to create green havens for their students, where they can learn, live and thrive in harmony with nature. These are some of the examples of how Nigerian campuses are creating green habitats for students. This development

is expected to help the socio-economic well-being of students. For instance, it has been noted that the responsibility of safeguarding the economy and putting in place infrastructure will boost development and enhance financial security so that people can provide for their basic needs. Putting in place green havens for students will help the socioeconomic and health conditions of members of the university community, thereby safeguarding their economy. University of Lagos (UNILAG), Ahmadu Bello University (ABU), Federal University of Technology, Minna (FUTMINNA) and University of Abuja and other tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Green Campus Initiatives

Green Campus Initiatives encompass a diverse array of programs, policies, and practices aimed at minimizing environmental impact and maximizing sustainability within the campus environment. These initiatives typically address various facets of sustainability, including energy conservation, waste reduction, water management, transportation, green spaces, and environmental education (Makemyassignment, 2024). Greening the campus is all about reducing wasteful practices. The use of non-conventional sources like solar energy and biomass energy can efficiently meet an educational institution's energy needs. The University can also purchase environment-friendly supplies and conduct an effective recycling program. Thus, energy efficiency and environmental sustainability should be the two pillars upon which the green campus concept needs to be based (GIETU 2021).

The aims of green campus initiatives of Middle East technical university, Northern Cyprus campus includes; to enhance efficiency in energy generation (produced by electrical generators), transmission and consumption on campus, to prevent inefficient or wasteful use of energy, to reduce carbon dioxide emissions on campus in order to achieve sustainable energy costs, to help the conservation of natural resources with the aid of a land use and rainwater management plan, to prevent environmental pollution with the aid of a waste management plan, to raise awareness of the issues of energy and environment in our community, to explore solutions to the impacts of climate change on the environment and human health (Middle East technical university, Northern Cyprus campus 2024)..

METHODOLOGY(METODOLOGIYA)

Literature Review

Green Campus Initiative

Green Campus Initiative is a program that plans, formulates, designs and implements a package of sustainable solutions by the campus community to reduce the environmental impact, enhance the campus sustainability and to protect the health and well-being of the surrounding community & ecosystems, implemented through selfless cooperation and coordination, by involving all stakeholders. The Green Campus concept offers an institution the opportunity to take the lead in rethinking its environmental culture and developing new paradigms for solving problems that are local, national, and global. It also presents a review of the approaches, methods and tools to inform, communicate and educate university students and the public on climate change being used by universities around the world (Association for promoting sustainability in campuses and communities 2021). From the above, Green Campus Initiative are programme designed for implementation in tertiary institutions to promote environmental sustainability in the campuses. Green Campus Initiative are planned and organized activities to ensure campuses are free from carbon emission.

Green Curriculum

Green curriculum emphasizes the interconnections between the environment, economy, and society, engaging students across cognitive, socio-emotional, and behavioral domains to inspire action for sustainability. Greening curriculum guidance: teaching and learning for climate action (UNESCO 2020). A

green curriculum integrates climate mitigation and adaptation in teaching and learning from pre-primary, primary, secondary and tertiary school levels as well as in teacher training. From the above, Green curriculum refer to a planned and organized learning instruction that focus on integration of climate education with aims of helping students understand and address the impacts of climate crisis, empowering them with knowledge, skills, value and attitudes for a friendly environment. Green curriculum refer to climate education at school's sustainability plan. It involves a combination of learning activities to promote environmental protection and conservation, waste management to aid environment sustainability.

Green Infrastructure facilities

Green infrastructure incorporates both the natural environment and engineered systems to provide clean water, conserve ecosystem values and functions, and provide a wide array of benefits to people and wildlife. Green infrastructure solutions can be applied on different scales, from the house or building level to the broader landscape level. On the local level, green infrastructure practices include rain gardens, permeable pavements, green roofs, infiltration planters, trees, and tree boxes, and rainwater harvesting systems. At the largest scale, the preservation and restoration of natural landscapes (such as forests, floodplains, and wetlands) are critical components of green infrastructure. Green infrastructure investments boost the economy, enhance community health and safety, and provide recreation, wildlife, and other benefits (Michigam & Eberle, 2024). Green infrastructure according to World green infrastructure (2020) refer to any vegetative infrastructure system which enhances the natural environment through direct or indirect means. It describes the network of green spaces and water systems that deliver multiple environmental, economical and social values and benefits for sustainable urban development. Green Infrastructure includes green roofs, living walls, parks and reserves, backyards and gardens, waterways and wetlands, streets and transport corridors, pathways and green corridors, squares and plazas, sports fields and cemeteries. Green Infrastructure provides and connects vital ecosystem services which contribute or enhance urban sustainability and the natural environment. From the above, green infrastructure facilities refer to super facilities designed to promote sustainable environment. Green infrastructure facilities are facilities designed to mitigate against climate change and carbon emission in campuses.

Funding Panacea for Development of Green Campus Initiatives in Nigerian Higher Education Institutions

Funding is very vital component of green programme. Funding will support development of green campus initiative programme, green curriculum and green infrastructure facilities.

Development of green campus initiative programme

Green Campus is an initiative involve all activities organized by student associations to prevent energy and water waste on campus. The Green Campus Initiative then further expanded to include more volunteers, particularly students, academic and administrative staff with an interest in the issue at hand. The aims and objectives of green campus initiative include; to enhance efficiency in energy generation (produced by electrical generators), transmission and consumption on campus, to prevent inefficient or wasteful use of energy, to reduce carbon dioxide emissions on campus in order to achieve sustainable energy costs, to help the conservation of natural resources with the aid of a land use and rainwater management plan, to prevent environmental pollution with the aid of a waste management plan, to raise awareness of the issues of energy and environment in our community, to explore solutions to the impacts of climate change on the environment and human health (Middle East technical university 2024)). Green campus initiative programme include; water management, soil conservation & sustainable food production, clean air, energy conservation, sustainable management of waste resources, sustainable use of natural resources, green facilities, green curriculum and student green club. The implementation of green

campus initiative programme require a lot of investment in both human and materials resources. Huge amount of monies are needed for the implementation of the programme in the various tertiary institutions. It is only special and adequate funding that can guarantee full development and implementation of the green campus initiative programme in the Nigerian tertiary institutions. Femi (2021) suggested that the government should increase the funding of tertiary institutions so that the institutions can implement the green campus initiative programme.

Development of green curriculum

Greening the curriculum means ensuring that students are capable of taking on the 21st century challenges of global warming and climate change (the most serious threat ever to face humanity), social inequities, unsustainable lifestyles, and the urgent need to switch to a renewable energy-based economy. Greening the curriculum means being open to Nature as Teacher, the outdoors as classroom, and sustaining life for all future generations as the most important learning objective in our curriculum (Green heart education 2023). The development of green curriculum and implementation require a lot of financial commitment by the school management. The development of green curriculum require consultancy with expertise and specialist in the field of environment science. The programme require training and retraining and provision of instructional resources. Large amount of funds will be needed to fully develop and implement the green curriculum in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Constant funding and adequate funding is required by the government and other education stakeholder in the management of the green campus initiative programme implementation. Sherif (2023) recommended that government should create special funding for the implementation of the programme in the tertiary institutions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION(NATIJALAR VA MUHOKAMA)

Development green infrastructure facilities

Green infrastructure has been defined as “A strategically planned network of natural and semi-natural areas with other environmental features, designed and managed to deliver a wide range of ecosystem services, while also enhancing biodiversity.” Such services include, for example, water purification, improving air quality, providing space for recreation, as well as helping with climate mitigation and adaptation. This network of green (land) and blue (water) spaces improves the quality of the environment, the condition and connectivity of natural areas, as well as improving citizens’ health and quality of life. Developing green infrastructure can also support a green economy and create job opportunities (European commission 2024). School benefits of green infrastructure includes; enhances community space and beautifies streets; Improves street conditions and safety for bicyclists and pedestrians; increases biodiversity and brings green to our neighborhoods; creates a more livable habitat for birds, native plants, and residents; recharges groundwater; reduces urban heat Island Effect; improves air quality; creates green jobs and reduces wastewater treatment costs and energy consumption (Sfpuc 2024).

Greening school facilities means designing (and then building or renovating/retrofitting and decorating) school environments that help students stay connected. The students learn what they live. If they spend all their school days in sterile classrooms, prison-like buildings and lifeless playgrounds, they will not become creative and critical thinkers, and they will not learn that human beings are a part of the beautiful web of life (Green heart education 2023). Adoption of green facilities in the schools will help in the development of green campus programme. The development of green infrastructure facilities in the various tertiary institutions is capital intensive. There is need for the government and other private institutions to provide adequate funds to support the various institutions in the development of green facilities in their respective institutions.

Findings

The paper discovered that funding is very vital component of green programme and adequate funding will support development of green campus initiative programme, green curriculum and green infrastructure facilities.

CONCLUSION(XULOSA)

This paper critically looked at the roles of funding in the implementation of green campus initiative in the Nigerian tertiary institutions and the paper concluded that without adequate funding nothing can be achieved in the programme of green campus in the Nigerian tertiary institutions. Funding will support development of green campus initiative programme, green curriculum and green infrastructure facilities.

Based on the findings, the paper recommends that federal government should establish a special intervention funding plans for the implementation of the green campus initiative in the Nigerian tertiary institutions. The international institutions and private institutions should be integrated into the funding programme of the green campus initiative in the Nigerian tertiary institutions. Government should set up effective monitoring and evaluation to monitor the use of the funds is allocated for the implementation of green campus initiative in the Nigerian tertiary institutions to curtail mismanagement of the funds.

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